

Supplemental Materials

to the publication entitled:

“Stability Analysis of Lunar Pit Slopes Considering Regolith Spatial Variability and Positional Uncertainty of the Regolith–Bedrock Boundary”

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Supplemental Material S1: Convergence tests

The Monte Carlo method was used to analyse selected cross-sections, where in each realization, unique random field realization is generated and/or unique boundary shape between regolith and rock. Such an approach is sensitive to the number of realizations. The accuracy of the estimates increases with the number of realizations. In this part a convergence tests are presented for the assumed 1,000 realizations, indicating that stable estimates of mean value and standard deviation are obtained for filtered data given in Supplementary Material J. The individual descriptions are provided in the subsequent figure captions, see Fig.S1 to Fig. S6.

Fig. S1. Convergence test for Scenario 2 and cross-section 0° ; a) mean value of the gravity multiplier; b) standard deviation of the gravity multiplier; c) mean value of the collapse area; d) standard deviation of the collapse area.

Fig. S2. Convergence test for Scenario 2 and cross-section 120° ; a) mean value of the gravity multiplier; b) standard deviation of the gravity multiplier; c) mean value of the collapse area; d) standard deviation of the collapse area.

Fig. S3. Convergence test for Scenario 2.3 and cross-section 0° ; a) mean value of the gravity multiplier; b) standard deviation of the gravity multiplier; c) mean value of the collapse area; d) standard deviation of the collapse area.

Fig. S4. Convergence test for Scenario 2.3 and cross-section 120° ; a) mean value of the gravity multiplier; b) standard deviation of the gravity multiplier; c) mean value of the collapse area; d) standard deviation of the collapse area.

Fig. S5. Convergence test for Scenario 3.1 and cross-section 0° ; a) mean value of the gravity multiplier; b) standard deviation of the gravity multiplier; c) mean value of the collapse area; d) standard deviation of the collapse area.

Fig. S6. Convergence test for Scenario 3.1 and cross-section 120° ; a) mean value of the gravity multiplier; b) standard deviation of the gravity multiplier; c) mean value of the collapse area; d) standard deviation of the collapse area.

Supplemental Material S2: Influence of threshold value in collapse area definition

The assumed procedure based on convex-hull plays a significant role in calculating the collapse area. In this study, a threshold value of velocity magnitude from FELA is set to 1/200 of the maximum velocity magnitude resulting from FELA for a given model. However, variations in this parameter may influence the calculated collapse areas. To assess the sensitivity to the collapse determination area, the collapse areas were recalculated using four values: 1/100, 1/200, 1/300, and 1/500. The resulting variations in the computed collapse areas are presented in Fig. S7 and Fig. S8 and summarized in Fig. S9 and Fig. S10.

Fig. S7. Histograms for different velocity thresholds and cross section 120°; a) Scenario 1; b) Scenario 2; c) Scenario 2.3; d) Scenario 2.4; e) Scenario 2.1; f) Scenario 2.2; g) Scenario 3.2; h) Scenario 3.1.

Fig. S8. Histograms for different velocity thresholds and cross section 240°; a) Scenario 1; b) Scenario 2; c) Scenario 2.3; d) Scenario 2.4; e) Scenario 2.1; f) Scenario 2.2; g) Scenario 3.2; h) Scenario 3.1.

Figure S9. Comparison of collapse areas mean values and standard deviations for cross-section 120° for four values of threshold, namely 1/500, 1/300, 1/200, and 1/100.

Figure S10. Comparison of collapse areas mean values and standard deviations for cross-section 240° for four values of threshold, namely 1/500, 1/300, 1/200, and 1/100.

Supplemental Material S3: Influence of regolith thickness distribution changes

In addition to uniform distribution of regolith thickness in range from 2 m to 10 m, the influence of the regolith thickness sampled from normal distribution with a mean value of 4 m and a standard deviation of 1 m is examined. The random boundary between regolith and rock was generated using the same procedure, but with different regolith thickness (see Table S1 and Fig. S11). As expected we have observed no significant impact, which is related to the fact that the regolith thickness affects the geometry of cross sections farther from the edge of the pit, where most of the collapses occur. Note that in this scenario, different boundaries between soil and rock were generated than those used in Scenario 3.2, but according to the same procedure. The total Monte Carlo analyses for both cases consider 1000 samples, where eight samples were excluded from newly calculated example due to errors in mesh generation, and 8 samples due to filtering as provided in Supplementary Material S10.

Table S1. Comparison of mean value and standard deviation for gravity multiplier and collapse area.

Assumed distributions for regolith thickness	Gravity multiplier		Collapse area	
	Mean value	Standard deviation	Mean value	Standard deviation
Unimodal U[2 m, 10 m]	5.19	2.64	21.56	16.91
Normal ($\mu=4\text{m}, \sigma=1\text{m}$)	5.33	3.01	21.62	16.56

Fig. S11. Spatially variable regolith properties and random boundary between regolith and rock for cross-section 120° (Scenario 3.2); a) regolith thickness described by unimodal distribution ranging from 2 m to 10 m; b) regolith thickness described by normal distribution with a mean value of 4 m and a standard deviation of 1 m.

Supplemental Material S4: Impact of vertical fluctuation scale

For comparison purposes, additional analyses for vertical correlation scale 10 m is presented in Fig. S12 with corresponding mean values and standard deviations provided in Table S2. This change will not introduce significant changes in the data distribution and mean values as shown in Fig. S12.

Fig. S12. Impact of vertical correlation length on gravity multipliers and collapse areas; (a,b,c) vertical correlation length 10 m; (e, f, g) vertical correlation length 5 m; (a, d) horizontal correlation length 5 m; (b, e) horizontal correlation length 10 m; (c, f) horizontal correlation length 50 m.

Table S2. Gravity multiplier and collapse area mean values and standard deviations for different vertical and horizontal correlation lengths for cross-section 120°.

Figure panel	Correlation lengths	Gravity multiplier		Collapse area	
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
S12a	Cy=5 Cx=5	2.21	0.286	13.98	13.65
S12b	Cy=5 Cx=10	2.21	0.301	15.09	16.65
S12c	Cy=5 Cx=50	2.21	0.323	15.79	18.40
S12d	Scenario 2.1	2.23	0.264	12.74	10.68
S12e	Scenario 2	2.23	0.292	13.79	13.21
S12f	Scenario 2.2	2.21	0.293	14.16	14.64

Supplemental Material S5: Impact of spatially variable cohesion

All results presented in the manuscript are related to constant cohesion value. Here, a lognormal random field is used to describe cohesion spatial variability with coefficient of variation 50% and mean value 1.154 kPa. The resulting mean values are comparable, but an increase in gravity multiplier is observed for spatially variable cohesion (the values are provided in the manuscript in the discussion section). The analyses provided in OptumG2 assumed by demould correlation coefficient 1 between random field of internal friction and cohesion, which represents the conservative scenario (when negative correlation will be assumed smaller difference in gravity multiplier standard deviation is expected).

Fig. S13. Comparison between scenario 2 for cross-section 120° and the same model settings with spatial variability of cohesion, a) scenario 2, b) spatial variability of cohesion included.

Supplemental Material S6: Impact of uncertainty in curvature radius determination

The assumption of axial symmetry is inherently connected with curvature radius determination. However, this determination can be uncertain due to irregular shape of the pit and its elliptical shape. The influence of this uncertainty was assessed by assuming the curvature radius from the neighbouring cross-sections, determined by each 10°. By analysing these values, the one with maximum relative differences is selected for the numerical analysis as presented in Table S3. The largest differences were observed at 240°. The resulting gravity multipliers mean values are: 9.07, 8.80, 8.62 and standard deviations: 4.89, 4.65, 4.59 for minimal, base and maximal radius of curvature, respectively, which result in approx. 5% range for mean value and 7% range for standard deviation. In case of collapse area, the results are as follows, for mean values are: 21.41, 22.07, 22.68 and standard deviations: 5.22, 5.21, 5.39, which result in approx. 6% range for mean values and 3% for standard deviations. Overall, the results suggest gradual influence of the radius of curvature on the results and uncertainty in local radius of curvature determination is not a source of large errors.

Table S3. Comparison of the radius of curvature in the previous, current, and next cross sections.

Cross section angle	Radius of curvature [m]	Radius of curvature for the previous segment [m]	Radius of curvature for the next segment [m]
0	45.11	46.66	44.59
40	49.21	46.66	52.67
80	65.28	61.24	68.17
120	65.28	68.17	61.24
160	49.21	52.67	46.66
200	45.11	44.59	46.66
240	56.82	52.67	61.24
280	69.22	68.17	68.17
320	56.82	61.24	52.67

Fig. S14. Comparison between models with different axial symmetry for Scenario 2 and cross-section at 240°; a) case with minimal radius of curvature (52,67 m); b) Scenario 2 (radius of curvature 56,82

m); c) case with maximal radius of curvature (61,24 m). Note: two realizations in panels (a) and (c) were excluded from the figure due to lack of convergence of the FELA method.

Supplemental Material S7: Cross-validation of FELA and strength reduction method

For validation, the results from FELA and the strength reduction method were combined. For each model, a safety factor was extracted and used to reduce the mean values of cohesion and the tangent of the friction angle in the FELA analysis (Fig. S15). The distribution of collapse area (panel G1b) follows closely the one observed for strength reduction method with mean value of 69.7 m² and standard deviation 17.9 m² versus mean value 72.0 m² and standard deviation 22.5 m² for strength reduction method.

Fig. S15. Comparison of results from FELA and the strength reduction method for Scenario 3.2; a) FELA (Scenario 3.2); b) FELA results obtained for strength parameters normalized by the safety factor; c) Strength reduction method.

Supplemental Material S8: Derivation of Eq. (2)

The derivation of this equation is based on a classical result from probability theory concerning the probability density function of a random variable under a transformation (it can be found in several classical book such as “A first Course in Probability” by Sheldon Ross (Theorem 7.1). Specifically, let X be a random variable with probability density function $f_X(x)$, and let $g(x)$ be a strictly monotonic and differentiable function. Then, the random variable Y defined by $Y = g(X)$ has a probability density function given by:

$$f_Y(y) = f_X(g^{-1}(y)) \left| \frac{d}{dy} g^{-1}(y) \right|$$

This expression is valid on the interval corresponding to the domain of X ; outside this interval, the probability density function is equal to zero.

In our case, the random variable X corresponds to K , the transformed variable Y corresponds to H_1 , and the transformation function $g(\cdot)$ is given by

$$H_1 = g(K) = 1.1 h_c \frac{K}{K + 1}.$$

The inverse transformation is

$$g^{-1}(h_1) = \frac{h_1}{1.1 h_c - h_1},$$

and its derivative with respect to h_1 is calculated from the derivative of a quotient of functions, and is

$$\frac{d}{dh_1} g^{-1}(h_1) = \frac{1.1 h_c}{(1.1 h_c - h_1)^2}.$$

Since K is uniformly distributed on the interval $(1,10)$, its probability density function is constant $f_K(k) = 1/9$. Substituting these expressions into the transformation formula provided at the very beginning yields the final probability density function of H_1 :

$$f_{H_1}(h_1) = \frac{1}{9} \frac{1.1 h_c}{(1.1 h_c - h_1)^2}, 0.55 h_c < h_1 < h_c,$$

while $f_{H_1}(h_1) = 0$ outside this interval.

Reference:

Ross, S. M. (2020). A first course in probability. Harlow, UK: Pearson.

Supplemental Material S9: Regolith parameters

The laboratory test data and conditions referenced in the manuscript are drawn primarily from NASA’s Apollo Soil Mechanics Investigation reports (e.g., Carrier et al., 1991), which provide triaxial compression, direct shear, unconfined compression, penetration resistance, and bulk-density measurements conducted under controlled vacuum and low-stress conditions representative of the lunar near-surface environment. Based on these tests, typical parameter ranges adopted in this study include bulk density values of approximately 1.3–1.8 g/cm³, friction angles of 30°–50°, and apparent cohesion values of 0.1–1.0 kPa for shallow mare regolith. In contrast, the Soviet mechanical data (e.g., Cherkasov & Shvarev, 1973) are based primarily on cone-vane penetration tests and compaction/void-ratio experiments performed on returned Luna regolith samples, from which bearing strength, shear resistance under vane-plate loading, compressibility, and stress–void-ratio relationships were derived. The dataset is determined for shallow depths (the near-surface regolith), generally within up to 80 cm (double-core sampling at several stations). Some of the Apollo cores were up to 3 m depth (Carrier et al., 1991), which is a direct confirmation of minimum regolith thickness in the landing locations.

It is emphasized that the dataset, including parameters of Martian regolith, was used exclusively in the preliminary Scenario 1; moreover, as indicated by the parameter ranges, these values are consistent with those adopted for lunar regolith and therefore do not significantly affect the final results. For this reason, these data were included; however, while both Martian and lunar regolith are influenced by impact-dominated mechanical fragmentation and lack active plate tectonics, these broad geological similarities alone are insufficient to justify the direct transfer of mechanical soil properties. Lunar and Martian regolith differ fundamentally in several aspects that directly control slope stability, including gravity level, mineralogical composition, degree of space weathering, particle angularity, cementation effects, and electrostatic interactions. Without explicit microstructural, mineralogical, or experimentally validated mechanical evidence demonstrating equivalence, the assumption of comparable mechanical behavior remains speculative.

Table S4. A brief summary of the mechanical parameters of lunar and Martian regolith available in the literature, based on data compiled from Knez (2021) and other studies.

No.	Mission name	Cohesion		Friction angle		Density	
		Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Minimum Value	Maximum Value	Minimum Value	Maximum Value
		[kPa]	[kPa]	[°]	[°]	[g/cm ³]	[g/cm ³]
1	Surveyor – Jaffe (1967)	0,15	15	55	55	-	-
2	Luna 13 – Cherkasov and Shvarev, (1973)	0.0005	0.0005	32	32	0.8	0.8
3	Lunar orbiter – Nordmeyer, (1967)	0,35	0,35	33	33	-	-
4	Surveyor 3 and 6 – Scott and Roberson, (1968)	0,35	0,7	35	37	-	-
5	Lunar orbiter – Moore, (1968)	0,1	0,1	10	30	-	-
6	Lunar orbiter – Hovland and Mitchell, (1970)	0,5	0,5	21	55	-	-
7	Apollo 11 - Costes et. al., (1970)	0,3	1,4	35	45	1.54	1.75

8	Apollo 11 - Costes et. al., (1971)	0.8	2.1	37	45	1.81	1.92
9	Apollo 12 – Costes et. al., (1971)	0.6	0.8	38	44	1.8	1.84
10	Luna 16 – Cherkasov and Shvarev, (1973)	0.01	0.03	29	35	1.26	2.21
11	Luna 20 – Cherkasov and Shvarev, (1973)	0.0015	0.0015	26	26	1.46	1.5
12	Apollo 14 – Mitchell et. al., (1971) –	0.03	0.4	35	45	-	-
13	Apollo 15 – Mitchell et. al., (1972)	-	-	49.5	49.5	1.97	1.97
14	Viking 1 – Moore, (1982)	0.4	2.8	15.6	20.4	1	1,3
15	Viking 1 – Moore, (1982)	2.4	7.8	28.4	33.2	1.56	1.64
16	Viking 1 and 2 – Moore, (1982)	1	10	40	60	2.6	2.6
17	Viking 2 – Moore, (1982)	0.3	1.9	29.8	39.2	1.2	1.6
18	Sojourner – Moore, (1997)	0	0.91	31.4	42.2	2	2.2
19	Sojourner – Moore, (1997)	0	0.71	15.1	33.1	1.07	1.27
20	Insight – Kalapodis, (2020)	1	2	-	-	-	-
21	Boulder track - Nordmeyer (1967)	0.35	0.35	33	33	-	-
22	Survyour 1 - Christensen (1967)	0.13	0.4	30	40	-	-
23	Survyour 3 - Scott and Roberson (1968)	0.35	0.7	35	37	-	-
24	Survyour 3 -Christensen (1968c)	0	10	45	60	-	-
25	Survyour 6 - Christensen (1968a)	0.5	1.7	35	35	-	-
26	Lunar Orbiter - Moore (1970)	0.1	0.1	10	30	-	-
27	Lunar Orbiter - Hovland and Mitchell (1971)	0.5	0.5	21	55	-	-
28	Apollo 12 - Costes (1971)	0.6	0.8	38	44	-	-
29	Apollo 14 met - Mitchell (1971b)	-	-	37	47	-	-
30	Costes (1972)	0	0.035	31	39	-	-
31	Apollo 11 – Costes et al. 1970	-	-	-	-	1.36	1.8
32	Apollo 12 – Jafé (1972)	-	-	-	-	1.15	1.93
33	Apollo 14– Mitchell (1972)	-	-	-	-	0.84	1.58
34	Apollo 15 – Mitchell (1972)	-	-	-	-	1.07	1.92
35	Luna XVI – Gromov et al. (1971)	-	-	-	-	1.12	1.79

Supplemental Material S10: Summary of Monte Carlo analyses

Table S5. Summary of Monte Carlo results for Scenario 1. The table presents the number of correctly analysed realizations (column 3), their mean values and standard deviations (columns 4 and 5), number of realizations after filtering the very large gravity multiplier values (column 6), and their mean values and standard deviations (columns 7 and 8). Columns 9-12 present number of realisations and their percentages from the filtered one (column 6) greater than mean values plus two standard deviations (columns 9 and 10) and greater than mean values plus three standard deviations (columns 11 and 12).

Scenario 1											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Cross Section [°]	Number of Monte Carlo realizations	Number of correctly analyzed realizations	Gravity multiplier mean value $\mu_{G(3)}$	Gravity multiplier standard deviation $\sigma_{G(3)}$	Number of realizations with gravity multiplier $< \mu_{G(3)} + 3\sigma_{G(3)}$	Gravity multiplier mean value $\mu_{G(6)}$	Gravity multiplier standard deviation $\sigma_{G(6)}$	Number of realizations with gravity multiplier $> \mu_{G(6)} + 2\sigma_{G(6)}$	Percentage of total number of realizations [%]	Number of realizations with gravity multiplier $> \mu_{G(6)} + 3\sigma_{G(6)}$	Percentage of total number of realizations [%]
0	1000	1000	1,466	1,4332	985	1,3205	0,6651	41	4,162	18	1,827
40	1000	1000	10,2856	101,7341	995	3,7448	12,6619	9	0,905	7	0,704
80	1000	1000	3,4972	13,8536	996	2,8197	3,0645	28	2,811	17	1,707
120	1000	1000	1,2956	0,865	985	1,2229	0,5771	47	4,772	19	1,929
160	1000	1000	2,3434	2,35	981	2,0907	1,2766	54	5,505	27	2,752
200	1000	1000	1,5715	1,4647	992	1,4883	0,8387	46	4,637	28	2,823
240	1000	1000	3,0812	4,256	985	2,6904	2,2097	52	5,279	28	2,843
280	1000	1000	1,5019	1,4576	986	1,3768	0,7667	47	4,767	21	2,13
320	1000	1000	1,0871	0,7992	982	1,0065	0,4388	57	5,804	18	1,833

Table S6. Summary of Monte Carlo results for Scenarios 2 and Scenarios 3. The table presents the number of correctly analysed realizations (column 3), their mean values and standard deviations (columns 4 and 5), number of realizations after filtering the very large gravity multiplier values (column 6), and their mean values and standard deviations (columns 7 and 8). Columns 9-12 present number of realisations and their percentages from the filtered one (column 6) greater than mean values plus two standard deviations (columns 9 and 10) and greater than mean values plus three standard deviations (columns 11 and 12).

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Scen.	Cross Section [°]	Number of Monte Carlo realizations	Number of correctly analyzed realizations	Gravity multiplier mean value $\mu_{G(3)}$	Gravity multiplier standard deviation $\sigma_{G(3)}$	Number of realizations with gravity multiplier $< \mu_{G(3)} + 3\sigma_{G(3)}$	Gravity multiplier mean value $\mu_{G(6)}$	Gravity multiplier standard deviation $\sigma_{G(6)}$	Number of realizations with gravity multiplier $> \mu_{G(6)} + 2\sigma_{G(6)}$	Percentage of total number of realizations [%]	Number of realizations with gravity multiplier $> \mu_{G(6)} + 3\sigma_{G(6)}$	Percentage of total number of realizations [%]
2	0	1000	1000	1,4774	0,1622	992	1,4725	0,1533	23	2,319	4	0,403
	120	1000	1000	2,2371	0,3073	993	2,2289	0,2922	43	4,33	2	0,201
	240	1000	1000	8,8154	4,6418	979	8,3528	3,2272	47	4,801	26	2,656
2.1	0	1000	1000	1,4778	0,1436	993	1,4744	0,138	38	3,827	3	0,302
	120	1000	1000	2,2411	0,2832	989	2,2299	0,2638	45	4,55	6	0,607
	240	1000	1000	8,504	3,7232	982	8,1724	2,716	47	4,786	14	1,426
2.2	0	1000	1000	1,4786	0,1697	994	1,4741	0,1596	36	3,622	5	0,503
	120	1000	1000	2,2203	0,3134	992	2,2105	0,2933	34	3,427	2	0,202
	240	1000	1000	10,1245	29,314	999	9,2206	6,5079	35	3,504	15	1,502
2.3	0	1000	1000	1,4666	0,0591	995	1,4656	0,0574	22	2,211	0	0
	120	1000	1000	2,2135	0,1125	996	2,212	0,1101	35	3,514	0	0
	240	1000	1000	8,1899	1,3837	990	8,1344	1,2689	40	4,04	6	0,606
2.4	0	1000	1000	1,524	0,4161	982	1,4912	0,3344	37	3,768	6	0,611
	120	1000	1000	2,2262	0,7217	983	2,1795	0,63	53	5,392	15	1,526
	240	1000	998	10,6565	54,3991	997	8,9561	8,5792	48	4,814	18	1,805
3.1	0	1000	1000	262,6679	2620,949	994	104,0528	296,8709	20	2,012	15	1,509
	120	1000	1000	5,2641	1,7253	1000	5,2641	1,7253	0	0	0	0
	240	1000	999	7,9301	1,0098	983	7,861	0,8447	33	3,357	11	1,119
3.2	0	1000	1000	163,7144	920,2491	993	103,1937	244,6505	38	3,827	18	1,813
	120	1000	992	5,5684	5,7122	984	5,1802	2,6467	48	4,878	13	1,321
	240	1000	1000	10,0333	16,1014	993	8,9269	5,4512	32	3,223	15	1,511
3.3	0	1000	1000	2,692	0,3567	990	2,6792	0,3341	43	4,343	3	0,303
	120	1000	1000	3,8782	0,7027	993	3,8594	0,6676	34	3,424	3	0,302
	240	1000	1000	8,9052	8,3197	990	8,3586	4,0751	50	5,051	24	2,424

Supplemental Material S11: Regolith thickness near pit wall

The average regolith thickness was calculated within a 10-meter radius from the point where the regolith starts (e.g., point 1 in Fig. 5). The obtained average regolith thickness values are presented together with the corresponding gravity multipliers for the three analyzed cross-sections (see figure S16). The results indicate that the average regolith thickness near the collapse edge may influence slope stability. This is visible for cross-section 0° (panels a and b in Fig. S16), where an increase in average regolith thickness at the toe of the regolith slope corresponds to a decrease in gravity multipliers. In contrast, cross-section 240° (panels e and f in Fig. S16) shows virtually no such effect. Therefore, the influence appears to be case-dependent and related to the geometry of the slope surface, which requires further detailed investigation.

Fig. S16. Gravity multipliers versus mean regolith thickness in the first 10 m of regolith layer; a, c, e) Scenario 3.1; b, d, f) Scenario 3.2; a, b) cross-section 0° ; c, d) cross-section 120° ; e, f) cross-section 240° ;